

[Shlomo David Rabi](#) is a Funding Coordinator at Kingdom Kapital, a company which provides financial support to a very wide range of SMEs. David Rabi works and lives in North York, Ontario, Canada. From November 2016 till May 2018 he worked as a senior account executive for Connex Telecommunication Inc., a national company with over 600 employees, which has evolved into a leading-edge systems integrator. Prior to joining Connex, Shlomo David Rabi, for almost two years, David Rabi was Sales Consultant at Star Power Ventures.

Kingdom Kapital offers affordable funding solutions for all industries in the nation. The company prides itself in providing fast and reliable funding solutions. Small Business Loans, Term Loans, Merchant Cash Advances and Lines of Cre.

From November 2016 till May 2018 he worked as a senior account executive for Connex Telecommunication Inc., a national company with over 600 employees, which has evolved into a leading-edge systems integrator. Prior to joining Connex, Shlomo David Rabi, for almost two years, David Rabi was Sales Consultant at Star Power Ventures.

Shlomo David Rabi holds a Bachelor of Arts Degree in Business Studies from Toronto University.